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Legal Expert

MINIMUM VIABLE SKILLS PROFILE

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Legal Expert

Minimum Viable Skills Profile

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Disclaimer

This booklet is part of the **Skills4EOSC collection of Minimum Viable Skills Profiles (MVS)**, which outline key Open Science competencies for different professional roles. It presents a focused extract from the **Annex to Deliverable D2.6**, designed to support usability and communication. To explore the full list of profiles, visit the Skills4EOSC website (<https://www.skills4eosC.eu/resources/publications/mvs>) or consult the full Annex (<https://zenodo.org/records/15761916>).

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics	MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
CSCCE	Centre for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement	ORCC	Open Research Competencies Coalition
DMP	Data Management Plan	OS	Open Science
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues	R&I	Research and Innovation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud	RDA	Research Data Alliance
ETHRD IG	Education and Training on Handling of Research Data Interest Group (RDA)	RDM	Research Data Management
ICT	Information and Communication Technology	RI	Research Infrastructure
IT	Information Technology	RPO	Research Performing Organisation
JRC	Joint Research Centre	RSE	Research Software Engineer
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable	T4fs	Terms for FAIR skills

1. Introduction

Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) for Legal Experts provides a structured understanding of the critical competencies required by professionals responsible for ensuring legal compliance within Open Science. These individuals play a key role in managing the complex legal landscapes surrounding both personal and non-personal data, safeguarding the rights of third parties while promoting openness and adherence to the **FAIR principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Legal Experts must navigate the tension between the existing property-based legal framework and the openness essential to achieving Open Science objectives, particularly in areas such as Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and data protection.

The term “Legal Expert” encompasses a variety of professionals, including Legal Consultants, Lawyers, Regulatory Affairs Managers, Data Protection Officers (DPOs), and Technology Transfer/IP Lawyers. Each role has varying degrees of legal authority, with some professionals, such as Regulatory Affairs Managers, not always licensed to provide legal advice yet having significant expertise in legal matters. A key aspect of this role is ensuring compliance with regulations such as the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**, while also facilitating open access to research materials, data reuse, and collaboration. Legal experts also assist in aligning organizations with legal standards, mitigating risks related to privacy, intellectual property, and contractual obligations.

An important responsibility of Legal Experts is bridging the gap between the goals of Open Science and regulatory requirements. They work closely with researchers and institutions to ensure that the use of protected materials and sensitive data complies with existing laws, while promoting openness and facilitating the lawful sharing and reuse of scientific information. Their work often includes drafting agreements, managing licensing, ensuring the preservation of protected materials, and advising on data-sharing practices.

The mission of a Legal Expert in Open Science is to promote openness and FAIRness in a legal system predominantly centred on exclusive property rights, while simultaneously mitigating legal risks through a proactive approach to compliance with personal and non-personal data regulations. In doing so, they contribute significantly to building a transparent and accessible research environment, which is critical for the advancement of Open Science.

LEGAL EXPERT

Legal experts play a critical role in ensuring that research practices, particularly in the context of Open Science, comply with complex legal frameworks. Their primary responsibility is to safeguard the rights of third parties by ensuring adherence to national, regional, and international regulations governing both personal and non-personal data. Legal experts manage the tension between traditional intellectual property laws, which are often based on exclusive ownership, and the openness required to advance Open Science goals. Their expertise is essential in mitigating legal risks, ensuring data protection, and promoting openness and compliance with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

ASSOCIATED FUNCTION TITLES:

Legal Consultant, Lawyer, Regulatory Affairs Manager, Technology Transfer/IP Lawyer, Data Protection Officer, Legal Advisor.

ESSENTIAL SKILLS FOR THIS ROLE

- Good understanding of OS and its practices.
- Ability to establish the appropriate strategy, frameworks and course of actions to foster and enhance OS.
- Expert knowledge of the FAIR principles and how to apply them, especially the one concerning (re)usability e.g. copyright licensing rules and existing frameworks like the Creative Commons licenses.
- Ability to identify ethical issues and apply the necessary measures to address the existing and applicable ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct, including but not limited to the ones concerning research, e.g. the RRI Framework and the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA).
- Ability to address legal issues related to personal data governance, including but not limited to the management of personal data; development and management of policies on privacy and data protection, e.g. consent forms, data policies, etc; and expert knowledge on the application of regulations concerning privacy and personal data protection.
- Ability to develop, negotiate and assess data use agreements, based on expert knowledge of the regulations that commonly govern these documents.

SOFT / TRANSVERSAL SKILLS

Considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

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|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problem-solving • Effective communication • Critical and Analytical thinking • Collaboration | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translating needs/bridging function • Research skills • Flexibility and adaptability • Proactiveness and responsiveness |
|---|--|

BACKGROUND ASSUMPTIONS

MAIN ACTIVITIES

- Promotes and supports Open Access and other Open Science related legal and ethical principles.
- Monitors the regulatory landscape and national policies concerning OS e.g. GDPR, ODD, DGA, Data Act proposal, IPR-related directives and regulations.
- Assesses and addresses legal risks concerning Intellectual Property Rights, e.g., Personal and Non-Personal Data Protection and Governance, Licensing and Information Security.
- Promotes Open Science by employing available instruments e.g. licensing frameworks, rights retention strategies; and normative tools e.g. copyright exceptions and limitations.
- Develops policies, contracts and other instruments needed to put into action the legal rules and ethical principles concerning OS.
- Advises the organisation about the compatibility of local practices with current legal frameworks.

CONTRIBUTES TO WHICH OPEN SCIENCE OUTCOMES?

- The organisation is able to adopt existing licensing frameworks e.g. Creative Commons, and enjoys the free uses allowed under the existing legal framework e.g. copyright limitations and exceptions.
- The organisation is equipped with policies, contracts and other instruments needed to apply the legal rules and ethical principles concerning Open Science.

Further information

OPEN SCIENCE SKILLS TERMS

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Manage Intellectual Property Rights](#); [Apply Research Ethics and Scientific Integrity Principles in Research Activities](#); [Manage Open Publications](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Solve Problems](#); [Identify Problems](#); [Show Initiative](#); [Comply with Regulations](#); [Negotiate Compromises](#); [Resolve Conflicts](#); [Organise Information, Objects and Resources](#); [Moderate a Discussion](#); [Think Critically](#); [Think Analytically](#); [Build Networks](#); [Demonstrate Intercultural Competence](#); [Demonstrate Trustworthiness](#); [Think Quickly](#); [Demonstrate Willingness to Learn](#); [Attend to Detail](#); [Demonstrate Curiosity](#).

ResearchComp: Strategic thinking; Systemic thinking; Analytical thinking; Cope with pressure; Plan self-organisation.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Knowledge to contextualise FAIR principles to domain](#); [Information security](#); [Data policy](#); [Ethical application of patents, licenses](#); [Data access risk assessment and mitigation](#); [Data driven decision management](#); [Research integrity, attribution, impact awareness](#); [Research governance](#); [Change management](#).

CSCCE: [Strategy development](#); [Content planning](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Speaking and presenting](#); [Consultation and listening](#); [Collaboration](#).

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